

UNDERGRADUATE SPECIAL PROJECT/CAPSTONE

Bachelor of Education Studies (BES)

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

BACHELOR OF EDUCATION STUDIES

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The MQP Joint-Project: Youth Ministry E-ntegration 1st Section

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Acceptance Page

This special/capstone project prepared by **ANTHONY JONATHAN TABILISMA ROSANTINA** with the title: “**The MQP Joint-Project: Youth Ministry E-ntegration 1st Section**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Education, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Education Studies.

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Biographical Sketch

The author of the capsule project, Anthony Jonathan T. Rosantina, is a Filipino born on the 17th day of August in the year 2001 and grew up in the municipality of Taytay in the province of Rizal as the eldest of two siblings within the family.

As an online distance learner under the Bachelor of Education Studies (BES) Program at the University of the Philippines Open University, his dedication towards serving the community and striving to become an educator had been an integral part in his academic journey. As an avid advocate of volunteerism, he participated in various donation drives and feeding programs for children hosted by his former school Golden Faith Academy. Moreover, he also serves his community as a member of the youth ministry in his local Parish.

He finds inspiration in making learning enjoyable and centered towards students through his teaching philosophy inspired from the likes of Lev Vygotsky and Jean Piaget as he believes that within every learner lies a dormant potential waiting to flourish through effective stimulation.

Acknowledgement

The accomplishment of this joint capsule project is dedicated towards everyone who helped bring the Project together despite all the challenges that were encountered. First and foremost, this project is dedicated to God and country as they both served as the primary inspiration in the creation and accomplishment of the project. Being that the capsule project was designed to be conducted jointly in cooperation with one other BES student and friend, Mark Chester Tating, due acknowledgement is also given to him as fellow designer and proponent. In a similar fashion, acknowledgement is also given to Sir Lex Mangubat and Sir Ley Gripal of the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU) as well as Father Manuel Cuevas, Sister Reynalda Habac, Sister Rosa Calderon, and Brother Angelito Andres of Mary the Queen Parish (MQP) for serving as the content experts and guiding mentors of the proponent throughout the design, implementation, and evaluation process of the capsule project. Of course, the same could be said for the main participants of the project, the BBS Core group, who similarly provided their utmost support during the implementation and evaluation of the materials produced. Above all else, I dedicate this project to God and my parents. Thus, I give my pure thanks to everyone who gave their utmost support and time in helping me accomplish this project.

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Abstract

This Capsule Project is part of a two-phase joint-intervention program targeted towards the chosen locale of Mary the Queen Parish (MQP), a religious institution under the Roman Catholic Christian denomination which also serves as an institution facilitating learning to parish members and church-goers through seminars and team-building activities. The uniqueness of the institution's context as a place wherein worship and learning occurs simultaneously underpins a delicate learning process that balances the Catholic doctrine with the conventional methods and strategies for learning. A field inspection and context analysis of the Institution revealed particular gaps and issues being faced by the parish which pertain to the need for instructional materials, manuals, and an exploration of technology-integration within the parish particularly on the part of the BA Core Youth Ministry which was identified to be inactive and scattered. In order to address these gaps, instructional design was utilized to design and create digital instructional materials and manuals that are print compatible which serves the purpose of helping resolve the aforementioned gaps within the institution. This phase of the joint-project focused on developing instructional materials to be used by the target learners during the BBS 1 youth seminar, with the developed materials garnering positive feedback from the target audience. With that said, feedback showed split preference between the digital and print version of the material. Length also became a deciding factor as the final combined output of the joined-project was deemed to be too lengthy which warranted changes in the sectioning and presentation of its content.

Keywords: Technology-Integration, Open Education, OERS, Non-formal Education

I. INTRODUCTION

Rationale

It is undeniable that education covers a wide range and variety of fields divided into three main categories of Formal Education, Non-Formal Education, and Informal Education. From these three main categories, the field of Formal Education remains to be the most well-studied and supported category with the latter two categories often being dismissed and left behind with little to no support which in turn makes institutions under these two categories a good target for an educational intervention in the form of a capsule project. Using this as the main qualifier, several educational institutions within the local community of the proponent were listed as the potential locales from which a religious institution by the name of Mary the Queen Parish stood out and was ultimately chosen as the target locale for the capsule project with the reason being that in today's rapidly evolving educational landscape post-pandemic era, the integration of technology in learning became hand in hand with each other. However, such is not often the case for non-formal educational institutions, such as churches which a lot of the times face challenges in adopting modern educational tools due to limited resources or lack of specialized training. In the case of Mary the Queen Parish, the institution has expressed a clear need for updated and appropriate learning materials that cater towards the Basic Bible Seminar to be attended by the church's youth ministry. Particular emphasis was given for the need to make the instructional materials aligned with the learning needs of the target audience, being that the current module being used by the church lacks accessible formats and appropriateness in terms of clearness and presentation of content in relation to the audience that it is targeted towards which are the youth ministry composed mostly of late teenagers and young adults. Through

introducing technology-integrated instructional materials that are context-appropriate while also maintaining compatibility with print, this capsule project helps ensure flexibility in the delivery and presentation of learning, thereby meeting requirements for both digital and traditional modalities for learning while at the same time ensuring content alignment. Furthermore, this approach taken for the capsule project proves to be particularly valuable and advantageous in settings technology access might vary between individuals which is an essential variable that should always be considered for technology-integration in learning. As for the target audience chosen for this capsule project which are the BA Core Youth group composed of members of the Youth Ministry, aside from them being the participants of the Basic Bible Seminar 1, they were chosen for the project due to the crucial role that the youth ministry play within the institution in fostering faith, community involvement, and spiritual development among young members within the parish. In this regard, providing them with engaging and appropriate learning materials would in turn support their educational and spiritual growth not only as participants of the Basic Bible 1 Seminar, but also as future facilitators of the said program. With all these taken into consideration, the project in essence revolves around finding a way to resolve the aforementioned challenges being faced by Mary the Queen Parish as a non-formal educational institution through exploring the application of modern educational practices in relation to the traditional teaching methods utilized by the parish. Through the data gathered from this project, the institution would be able explore more avenues for improvement in delivering learning that would in turn help enhance its educational offerings through promoting a conducive learning environment that resonates with the audience that it is targeted towards.

Executive Summary

Following the three categories of education, it is evident that learning is not solely confined within the walls of a school's classroom as it can occur and transpire in various ways outside of the formal education system in the form of informal and non-formal education. In this particular case, the project aimed to explore learning in the context of a non-formal educational institution as it presents a unique environment of learning accompanied by a distinct set of challenges. With this in mind, the proponent of the capsule project decided to choose Mary the Queen Parish located in Meralco Subdivision, San Juan, Taytay, Rizal as the target locale which is a Roman Catholic Parish that is under the Vicariate of the St. John the Baptist of the Roman Catholic Church within the Diocese of Antipolo and was established in 2002.

Aside from it serving as a non-formal educational institution, the parish was chosen as the target locale by the proponent for several reasons. First and foremost, the proponent wanted to choose an organization or institution located within their immediate community. This was decided in consideration of the proximity of the location to the proponent in the context of ease of transport as well as their desire to give back to their local community as part of their advocacy as a student scholar. Second, the subject of religious houses of worship as institutions wherein learning occurs offers a unique learning environment different from the learning environment featured in secular educational institutions wherein the focus is on Scientific belief as opposed to the former which focuses on religious texts and doctrines. Furthermore, churches also encompass a wide variety of youth, adolescent, and adult learners

from all walks of life which broadens the potential target audience that the project proposal can reach out to. Similarly, the emerging integration of technology and digitalization in the learning process which is the chosen subject of the proponent for the capsule project can be applied in the context of religious education which makes it a good institution to serve as a target locale.

To provide further background, the Parish is relatively large in terms of space and area size, complete with various equipment utilized by the Catholic Church in various traditional ceremonies such as during Masses or during Baptism. As observed, among those commonly used during the aforementioned events are laptops, televisions, microphones, speakers, and screen projectors. Moreover, the atmosphere of the Parish when in use during masses is very strict yet solemn, with every participant listening intently and following the instructions that were given to them such as when asked to stand up, to pray, and to sing which are the three most conducted activities during masses.

From an educational standpoint, the process of learning being exhibited during learning sessions and seminars within the church typically follows the format of a Mass, with the instructor teaching in front of the learners while the learners would intently listen and would be occasionally be given opportunities to ask questions via raising their hands to indicate that they have something to say. Such a learning method mirrors that of a traditional learning method in which an instructor would provide information to the learners and would in turn passively absorb what is being taught to them.

Zooming in specifically on the youth ministry members which ages are on the 13-35 year old bracket, through observations and discussions with the Parish Priest, they were described to be learners that were primarily driven by engagement and entertainment which is backed up by their low participation rate for normal learning and meeting sessions when compared to their high participation rate during outdoor events. A similar case had been observed with regards to a subset of the youth ministry members which are the CORE BA youth ages 18 and up being trained to be the future Basic Bible Seminar 1 facilitators. Through initial observations and discussions with the parish priest, the proponent was able to uncover the particular gaps and issues being faced by the parish which pertain to the need for instructional materials, manuals, and an exploration of technology-integration within the parish particularly on the part of the youth ministry which was identified to be inactive and scattered.

Due to the wide scope of the challenges being faced by the institution, a collaboration between two individuals was needed to accomplish it which transformed the capsule project into a joint-project that was designed following the overarching goal of helping revitalize the youth ministry of Mary the Queen parish through addressing the gaps identified in the institution, namely the lack of trained youth facilitators and instructional materials to be utilized for the Basic Bible Seminar 1 as discussed earlier. Hence, the approach taken for the joint-project consists of two main parts, first one being the **development of appropriate instructional materials** to be utilized for these seminars in response to the lack thereof, and the second one being the **development of instructional manual** that would serve as a

guide material for members of the youth Ministry in aid of developing their skills and knowledge as one of the gaps that had been identified early on during observations and discussions with father Manuel and other parish members. A combination of both these aspects of the project would not only help address both individual gaps, but also the overarching goal of the joint-project of **revitalizing the youth ministry**. As part of the joint-project, this paper focuses on the first part which revolves around the development of appropriate instructional materials for the Basic Bible Seminar 1 that are underpinned by the two main themes of technology-integration and open education. In this particular case, content from the previous learning materials being used by the institution for the seminar were gathered and analyzed to be overhauled and reorganized as the content for the new instructional materials that were developed. Several main theories and concepts of learning were utilized by the proponent side by side with the Training Cycle Model to guide this process, namely Skinner's theory of Behaviorism, Sweller's Cognitive Load theory, Mayer's Multimedia Learning Theory, and Nash's Visual Principles of Instructional Media and Technologies for Learning. In essence, these theories and concepts were built as the backbone in the process of redesigning and aligning the content of the instructional material to the objectives of the seminar as well as to the learning needs and preferences of the target audience. Four types of learning materials were produced by the proponent which compose of (1) prayers, (2) songs, (3) Bible Verses, and (4) conference topics 1,2,3 and 4 of the basic Bible Seminar 1. Afterwards, these individual materials were combined accordingly with the materials created by proponent 2 in the second part of the joint-project to form a cohesive material in the form of an overhauled Basic Bible Seminar 1 Module which came in digital and printed form. Upon receiving approval from the project gatekeeper and the content

experts, a trial run in the form of a controlled module distribution immediately followed by an online pilot testing seminar had been initiated to scope validity of its content for the seminar as well as to gauge the opinion and perception of the target audience towards the finished module. The gathering of feedback from the target audience was accomplished through a feedback and evaluation survey form accomplished by the target audience digitally through google forms which was provided during the pilot testing seminar wherein a question-and-answer portion and an open forum was created to provide the audience multiple avenues for providing feedback and suggestions that reflect their experiences in testing the module which lasted for about a week. An analysis of the data gathered from the target audience revealed overwhelmingly positive feedback from the target audience with regards to the alignment and validity of the content, its arrangement, and how it was presented in the module through the incorporation of multimedia principles for learning. Another aspect of the material that they found to be advantageous points toward its flexibility as a conveniently modifiable learning material that can be repurposed through altering sections of the content. With that said, a consensus has not been reached with regards to which between the digital and the printed version is more preferred as the learning material since feedback from the target audience showcased a 50-50 split for which is more preferred. Upon analysis, this 50-50 split decision stemmed from a difference in the priorities considered by the target audience, with concerns being raised ranging from the cost of producing a printed module in mass for distribution being too costly to concerns about the digital module being too unwieldy for individuals who have limited skills in handling and navigating technology. Lengthiness also became a topic of contention during the evaluation phase as a number of individuals from the target audience deemed the module composed of

around 200 pages in total too lengthy when produced in printed form as opposed to its digital counterpart which can be divided into sections through selective downloading. Taking all of these into consideration, it can be argued that technology-integration proves to be valuable for Mary the Queen parish as an educational institution that provides learning to its members through seminars which is especially the case for its younger members who were the target audience of this capsule project. With that said, the allotted time for pilot testing had only been 1 week and so the feedback gathered was only limited to the said time frame that the target audience were given to test the product. Following the results of the capsule project, the proponent highlights the following findings and recommendations: (1) Instructional materials should be compatible with various formats in order to increase the ways in which it can be accessed; (2) users should be able to distribute, remix, and adapt the material conveniently in order to maximize its usability and adaptability to fulfill various needs within an institution; basic digital literacy skills are a must in the move towards digital-integration and so steps towards accomplishing it are a necessity; and that ample time should be allotted for the pilot testing of the product to provide the target audience more opportunities to test the product as a long term instructional material.

Objectives

Goals and Objectives of the Joint Project:

As a joint-project, the designing and developing of outputs to address the gaps identified would be divided into two, one for the material to be developed in response

to the identified gap pertaining to the lack of appropriate instructional materials within the parish to be handled by proponent A and another one, developed by proponent B for the manual to be developed in response to the gaps identified which pertain to the lack of instruction manuals and trained facilitators for seminar trainings conducted within the parish. To address the other gap pertaining to the lack of effective utilization of technology in instruction, a similar objective would be set for both the materials and the manual to be developed which is to introduce technology-integration to the Parish through both outputs (Material & Manual) to be designed and developed.

Personal Objectives of the Proponent:

The Personal goals and objectives of the Project's author are reflected in the initial gaps that were identified from Ocular Observations and Discussions with Father Manuel that needs to be addressed, namely the lack of youth member activity within the church which the project attempts to address through the gamification of the learning process within the church as is the initial plan for the project.

Another objective pertains to another gap found that similarly needs to be addressed, namely the lack of teaching staff or youth leaders capable of teaching youth members regarding spiritual life and the continuation of such a life which can be addressed by integrating technology-based tools to both lessen the teaching burden on the leaders and make learning more interesting for both youth leaders and members. Such goals and objectives extended towards the material developed under the project as the main aim had been to develop a material that would continue to be utilized and developed even after the project had officially ended. With

that said, as always, it is my personal goal to see to it that the project be fully realized and leave a permanent mark in the Institution.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Role of Instructional Materials in Academic Performance

Academic Performance had been regarded as one of the primary metrics utilized in measuring the learning that had transpired. Commonly defined as the student's ability to meet academic expectations, it is measured through a combined assessment primarily composed of a learner's computed grades in written tests and performance tasks alongside accomplished academic achievements and feats. As a driver of learning, instructional materials similarly play a key role in increasing academic performance. According to Miremba, B. (2024), instructional materials contribute to increased academic performance by improving the learners' understanding, engagement, memory retention, adaptability to diverse learning needs and preferences, critical thinking, and real-world experience. Of course, the appropriateness and applicability of the instructional material remain a significant factor in determining its effectiveness when utilized in a specific context considering how instructional materials vary in mode and instrument with each mode having its own specific affordances and limitations as discussed by Nunes and Gaible (2002) under their Table of Affordances and Limitations of Modalities.

Technology Integration and its effects in the field of Education

According to UNESCO (2024), the continuous major developments and advancements in the field of technology, especially digital technology, is driving the world into a rapid change as is the case in the field of education in the past 20 years wherein digital technology tools have been widely adopted by almost 50% of the world's lower secondary schools composed of institutions, teachers, and learners alike in 2022. In the 2023 Global Monitoring report by UNESCO, the potential of technology integration in resolving key educational challenges pertaining to (1) Equity and Inclusion, (2) Quality, and (3) Efficiency had been outlined and discussed.

Starting with its impact on equity and inclusion, the report discussed how ICT and digital technology is able to reduce the costs of education for challenged individuals especially for learners who have special needs and those who live in remote areas through expanded access to education via digital technology and assistive technology.

Moving on to the topic of education quality, the UNESCO Global Education Monitoring report (2023) discussed the potential benefits of technology integration in the quality of education through enhancing learning by creating engaging learning environments and facilitating collaboration as well as expanding connectivity and access which are held back by challenges like health risks, data misuse, and the spread of misinformation. Last but not the least, in the case of Efficiency, as discussed in the report, digital technology is able to offer diverse ways and methods to enhance learning efficiency in education such as reducing the time spent by learners and teachers alike on menial tasks which in turn frees up time for more meaningful and important educational activities.

Open Education as a driver of Accessibility and Inclusivity in Education

In the field of education, equity and inclusion remain a key challenge that inhibits learning especially for challenged and disadvantaged groups of individuals. According to a study conducted by Okongo, R. et al (2015) at a pre-school level academic institution, one of the causes that perpetuate this challenge points toward issues concerning the availability of appropriate teaching and learning materials that support accessibility and inclusivity.

The study concluded that challenges to acquisition and procurement of said materials due to issues such as the lack of resources for the procurement as well as the availability of the materials in the market influences the implementation of inclusive education. For instance, in a study conducted by Kurelovic, E. (2016) on the use of Open educational resources in small countries, he found out that although most teaching materials are available online, access to it is locked behind a barrier with only 20% of the available materials being accessible without barriers which ties into the issue of accessibility of materials underpinning the challenge of inclusivity in education.

In this regard, the use of Open Educational materials would prove to be valuable as according to Kurelovic, E. (2016), it enriches traditional teaching through enabling collaboration via the creation and sharing of open-access and easily adaptable instructional materials in online communities created for the purpose of exchanging ideas and knowledge using the materials which is well able to help open accessibility to instructional materials online.

Theoretical Framework:

Application of Technology-Integration and Open Education

Two theories are utilized as the main approach towards the designing of the materials which are Technology-integration and Open Education approach. Starting with the former, according to Hew, K. F. & Brush, T. (2007), technology integration in the context of education is an approach to teaching and learning that may come in various forms such as the use of technology to create assessments and activities or in the development of instructional materials in support of learning. This is one of the main approaches and strategies to learning utilized and applied for the joint-project as one of the main observations within the institution had been the lack of utilization of technology to support learning. Although there is equipment available to be used such as projectors, tv monitors, hdmi cables, and computers, not all of its functions and features are being utilized to its full potential as a means to improve the learning process. A similar case had been observed with regards to the use of social media to the advantage which had also been one of the initial plans for the project.

Furthermore, the utilization of instructional technology and media in the context of the learning-teaching process as discussed by Naz, A. A. & Akbar, R. A. (2008) opens up more opportunities for learning to engage deeper in their education such that when it is properly designed, skillfully produced, and effectively utilized, the instruction and learning process is elevated through enhanced effectiveness of communication that instructional technology and media provides. Which is to say, when utilized properly, the use of instructional technology and media in the context of learning-teaching process according to Naz, A. A. & Akbar, R. A. (2008) is able to improve said process in the following ways: (1) save time, (1) increase the interest of

learners, (3) maintain attention throughout the instruction, (4) help clarify ideas, (5) reinforce concepts for better information retention, (6) add tone for emphasis, (7) prove a point, and (8) aid the memory of learners.

As for the latter approach, according to Clinton-Lisell, et al. (2023), Open education is the term used for a particular approach in developing and using resources, materials, and pedagogies wherein they are made freely accessible and shareable with others through open and flexible licensing which is done through the Creative Commons Licensing. In support of the educational initiative towards addressing the ever increasing barrier to entry for formal education which increases the risk of more and more individuals not being able to afford formal learning due to the cost of textbooks and learning materials. In this regard, the final version of the material to be developed after passing all the checks from the institution would be licensed under creative commons to allow for a much more flexible use and remixing of the material. Through this step, the final material to be turned over to the institution could be easily utilized and remixed for other use and purposes that it may serve.

Considering the two aforementioned approaches utilized in the design direction of the materials to be created, it follows that the materials to be created would primarily be in digital form as it best allows the proper application of the two main approaches utilized in the creation of the materials which are the principles of Open Education and technology-integration. Following the classifications/types of media as outlined by Kemp, J. E. & Daylon, D. K. (1998), the following materials to be developed would fall under categories of Graphic Material which is composed of overhead

transparency Charts, graphs Models, dioramas, Maps, and globes and Photographic Material which is primarily composed of Still Pictures, Slides, Filmstrips, Motion pictures, and Multi-images.

Instructional Design

The model that was applied to guide the whole process of the joint-project was actually Beich, E. (2016)'s Training Cycle Model derived from the ADDIE model. Similar to the latter, the Training Cycle Model is composed of 5 Stages which are as follows: (1) Analysis, (2) Design, (3) Development, (4) Implementation and (5) Evaluation. As a sequential model, the sequence of these stages is non-interchangeable, meaning that these stages follow a specific order such that each stage must first be completed before moving on to the next. Which is to say, in this Training Cycle, the sequence of steps become s crucial for the process to work correctly. Using this model as the guide, the proponent was able to plan out the whole span of the joint-project from start to finish divided into 5 main phases each reflecting the stages of the Training Cycle Model.

Conceptual Framework

The project will be designed following the two aforementioned themes of technology-integration and open education with the process being guided by the Training cycle model derived from the ADDIE model. The project would revolve around the development of digital print-compatible instructional materials that combine into a module to be utilized by the BA core youth group (target audience) as an instructional material for the Basic Bible Seminar 1.

The material would build upon and reconstruct the contents included in the previous BBS 1 module through the use of instructional design models and principles following the two main themes. Afterwards, a week would be spent on the initial pilot testing of the material in collaboration with key individuals from the institution wherein the validity and accuracy of the material as well as the perception of the target audience would be evaluated and assessed as feedback for the improvement of the module in the aspects that it had excelled and what aspects it should improve upon in the context of resolving the gaps found in the institution that the project that is aiming to help resolve.

Operational Definition of Terms:

Technology-Integration - In the context of the project, the term refers to the use and utilization of technology for the purpose of enhancing and elevating the learning process provided by the chosen institution to its members via seminars.

Open Educational Resources - These refer to the instructional plans, instructional materials, and research that are published under an open license such as the Creative Commons License which in turn allows for free use, redistribution, and adaptation depending on the specified terms of use included in the license.

III. METHODOLOGY

Project Locale

The chosen locale by the proponents of the proposal is the Mary the Queen Parish (located in Meralco Subdivision, San Juan, Taytay, Rizal. It is a Roman Catholic Parish that is under the Vicariate of the St. John the Baptist of the Roman Catholic Church within the Diocese of Antipolo and was established in 2002. The Parish is relatively large in terms of space and area size, complete with various equipment utilized by the Catholic Church in various traditional ceremonies such as during Masses or during Baptism.

The atmosphere of the Parish when in use during masses is very strict yet solemn, with every participant listening intently and following the instructions that were given to them such as when asked to stand up, to pray, and to sing which are the three most conducted activities during masses.

From an educational standpoint, the process of learning being exhibited during learning sessions within the church typically follows the format of a Mass, with the instructor teaching in front of the learners while the learners would intently listen and would be occasionally be given opportunities to ask questions via raising their hands to indicate that they have something to say.

Zooming in specifically on the youth ministry members which ages are on the 13-35 year old bracket, through observations and discussions with Father Manuel, they were described to be learners that were primarily driven by engagement and

entertainment which is backed up by their low participation rate for normal learning and meeting sessions when compared to their high participation rate during outdoor events. A similar case had been observed with regards to a subset of the youth ministry members and this project's main target audience which are the CORE BA youth ages 18 and up being trained to be the future BBS 1 facilitators.

The Target Audience

The initial target audience for this project are the Mary the Queen Youth Ministry Members who according to the discussions with the Parish Priest father Manuel Cuevas had been scattered and uninvolved within the Parish, hence the need to revitalize ministry and re-engage them back to the parish. Upon review and consideration of the available resources and the allotted time frame for the project, this initial target audience pool size was deemed to be exceedingly large to be a feasible scale for the project. Hence, a second round of screening had been conducted to scale down the quantity of the target audience to which it was decided upon to choose a specific subset within the group to focus on, which in this case were the BA Core Group Members. The BA Core Group consists of individual youth members from the parish who were all passers of the Basic Bible Seminar 1 and are being trained to be the next facilitators of the future Basic Bible Seminar 1 to be conducted again by the Parish.

This subset of individuals from the Youth Ministry were chosen for the joint-project due to the following reasons. First, their context perfectly fits the goals and objectives of the joint-project of developing instructional materials and an instruction manual specifically targeted towards youth leaders and members to be utilized for seminars

conducted within the church. In this case, their background as facilitators-in-training would reflect their need for instructional materials and manuals not only for themselves but also for the future BA core group members which as per identified in the initial discussions and observations conducted had been the particular gaps within the institution. Secondly, considering how the future Basic Bible Seminar 1 is being planned to be primarily conducted and facilitated by the youth members for their fellow youth members, the issue of gaps in age (youth is considered those from the range of 13-31 yrs. Old and single) would be resolved as the age range of primary target participants for the Basic Bible Seminar 1 are teens to young adults which primarily compose of high-school to college level youth, thereby eliminating the need to consider Adults and Elementary level members for the project. Last but not the least, their background allows the project to focus solely on their context in designing and developing the materials and instruction manual which would be tailored for the Basic Bible 1 Seminar.

Analysis Phase

The needs assessment process that was conducted in the analysis stage of the joint-project was through a combination of ocular observations within the parish during masses and events, unstructured informal interviews with parish members, and discussions with father Manuel. These discussions tackle two main topics pertaining first to the background of the parish and the background of the constituents/members of the parish. Through these two themes, we were able to uncover the particular gaps and issues being faced by the parish which pertain to the need for instructional materials, manuals, and an exploration of

technology-integration within the parish particularly on the part of the youth ministry which was identified to be inactive and scattered. In particular, the primary information that we gained from this assessment was from an in-depth interview we did with father Manuel. During the session, the first question addressed was what defines a youth within the parish.

Through discussion, it was established that a youth is someone aged 13 and older who is single. Following this, we delved into Father Manuel's vision and overall goals for the project. He expressed his hope that our project would encourage greater youth engagement within the parish. He also emphasized that the materials and manual we are developing should have a lasting impact, continuing to be used well beyond the project's completion. The conversation then shifted to the challenges facing the Youth Ministry. It was revealed that there is a significant shortage of suitable instructional materials and manuals tailored to the learning needs of the youth in the parish. Additionally, Father Manuel highlighted that despite having a structured leadership in place, the ministry remains inactive, disjointed, and poorly organized. This was evident from the fact that many youth members participate only in events they find entertaining, while avoiding those they consider boring. As a recognized ministry within the church, the youth ministry is expected to be more engaged and involved in parish activities, such as assisting with event logistics, including arranging chairs and welcoming guests. It also became apparent that youth leaders and facilitators lack the skills to effectively utilize available resources, which hinders their ability to fully engage with the youth.

Thus, It was revealed that there is a significant shortage of suitable instructional materials and manuals tailored to the learning needs of the youth in the parish. Moreover, as a recognized ministry within the church, the youth ministry is expected to be more engaged and involved in parish activities, such as assisting with event logistics, including arranging chairs and welcoming guests. It also became apparent that youth leaders and facilitators lack the skills to effectively utilize available resources, which hinders their ability to fully engage with the youth. After the information and data gathered from the initial set of ocular observations and conversations with the local Parish Priest were compiled for review, a birds-eye view of the whole organization was able to be created which consists of three main parts which are the the (1) background of the parish, (2) the background of the parish members, and the (3) initial gaps identified in the institution.

A. Background of the Parish as a educational institution

The parish can be considered a unique Learning Institution since learning transpired here in the form of the Parish conducting Seminars for its Members

B. Background of the Parish Ministries and its Members

From the Ocular Observations and Discussions with the local parish priest father Manuel Cuevas, we found out that aside from the typical church-goers, the members of the Mary the Queen institution is divided into multiple ministries from which we identified four ministries which are the (1) Youth Ministry, the (2) Catechist Ministry, the (3) Worship Ministry, and the (4) Social Ministry. Starting with the Youth Ministry, these are members of the Parish who were ages 13 and above and should have a single status. Next up is the Catechist Ministry which are composed of members of

the church who are considered experts and More-Knowledgeable-Others in teaching the doctrine of the Catholic Church. Afterwards is the Worship Ministry composed of members of the parish who are tasked with leading the praise and worship sessions during various events and activities for the Parish. Last but not the list is the Social Welfare Ministry which is composed of volunteer members of the parish who are focused on humanitarian aid. From the aforementioned list of Ministries in the Parish that were identified, it was decided upon that it is best to choose among the list one particular Ministry which would serve as the focus group from which the target audience of the project would be chosen from. They are the most malleable that can be utilized to fit other purposes from activities of the different ministries.

C. Gaps Identified in the Institution

Through ocular observations and interviews conducted within the parish and relevant personnel such as the local parish priest and long-time parish volunteer workers, it was identified that the issue of lack of adequate learning materials and manuals had been particularly evident within the youth ministry which made them the primary choice to make as the target audience for the joint-project being planned. Aside from this, the gap identified much earlier from the initial observation and conversations done with the parish members during the previous event, namely the lack of alternative options to watch and engage with events which can be achieved via effective use and integration of technology, was also included as part of the gaps to be addressed through the project.

Design Phase

Attending the Basic Bible 1 Seminar:

Attending the Basic Bible Seminar 1 became the anchor in the design process and direction of the joint-project through the events that had transpired throughout and after the seminar. These are as follows:

- **Increase in Knowledge About the Catholic Doctrine:** The Basic Bible Seminar 1 conducted by the parish discussed 4 main conference topics, all pertaining to a similar theme which is the Bible. Considering how the proponent have no prior knowledge with regards to the doctrines of the Catholic church which is supposed to be the main content of the materials to be developed, acquiring more knowledge about the topic proved to be useful as I now have firsthand knowledge on particular set of topics discussed in seminars which is about the bible.
- **Receiving the Basic Bible 1 Seminar Certificate:** As the designer of the materials to be developed for use of the youth ministry within the parish, it is important for the proponent to be valid and credible as a designer to gain the trust of the target audience and the higher-ups within the parish in the case that the material would require their approval via a screening process. In this regard, the Basic Bible 1 Seminar Certificate that the proponent was able to acquire boosted their credibility as an individual knowledgeable about the topic even if they were not directly connected to the parish.

- **Meeting the youth members within the parish:** The primary target audience that the Basic Bible Seminar 1 was targeted towards are the youth ministry members of Mary the Queen parish. With the target audience of the project similarly being members of the youth ministry, these 2 days came as a golden opportunity to get to meet the members of the youth ministry and slowly introduce ourselves using the rapport that was built through attending the Basic Bible Seminar 1 which proved to be a success as we get to be acquainted with some members of the youth ministry.
- **Meeting the BBS 1 Head Facilitator:** Another success that can be attributed to attending the Basic Bible 1 Seminar was meeting Sister Rosa, one of the head-facilitators and organizers of the Basic Bible Seminar 1 alongside Kuya Angel. In particular, Sister Rosa's position within the parish as the Ministry of Evangelization and Lay Formation Coordinator made her a very valuable source of information and advice considering how she has access to a lot more information and materials within the parish as compared to the other members of the youth ministry. In this regard, I opted to make sister Rosa my main source of information and guidance aside from father Manuel throughout the project moving forward.
- **Acquiring the Basic Bible Seminar 1 Module:** through continued coordination and discussion with Sister Rosa, I was able to acquire the Basic Bible Seminar 1 module that they are using to conduct the BBS which became the primary source material that I used in the design process of the materials that I would be making.

Finalized Design Outline:

After reviewing the module, it was realized that a redesigned version of it would be the best option to be the main material output of the project since it already has a streamlined and specified purpose and is in urgent need considering the soon to start training for trainee-facilitators.

Now with a solid reference document in the form of the Basic Bible Seminar 1 module which was quite bare with it only having text while at the same time having low resolution due to it only being a scanned copy, the proponent coordinated with Proponent 2 to make it as the main material that would be used to pattern the output moving forward.

After talks and discussions, the proponent opted to proceed with redesigning the module through keeping the main content intact while applying various theories and principles to create a digital one that is more clear to read and is compatible to be printed as a booklet that can be physically produced and disseminated by the parish to the trainee-facilitators of Basic Bible Study 1.

Types of Materials to be developed:

In this regard, following the initial task that the proponent took which pertains to the development of materials for the parish, the parts of the module that was handed are the learning materials included within the original Basic Bible Seminar 1 module that they were able to acquire which are digital materials containing (1) prayers, (2) songs, (3) Bible Verses, and (4) conference topics 1-4. In preparation for the implementation, an additional material was also created which was the Participatory Certificates.

Issues identified in the Original Basic Bible 1 Seminar to be Overhauled:

- **Fully in Text-form:** The Original BBS 1 module is fully composed of text with no illustrations and organization of the content being talked about.
- **Monochrome:** The Original BBS 1 module, aside from not having illustrations, also lack color for appeal to its users which make it appear bland and uninteresting for the viewers which would especially be the case for youth members of the parish
- **Low Quality/Resolution:** The Original BBS 1 module is a low-quality digital scanned copy of a photocopy which makes a lot of the words hard to understand visually as they are either blurry or covered by black streaks. Moreover, some words are straight up incomplete due to the paper not being scanned properly.
- **Unaligned with MQP BBS 1:** The Original BBS 1 module which originally came from the Diocese of Antipolo is designed to be implemented for 5 nights whereas the parish's BBS 1 is being conducted for 2 days as seen in the invitation shown earlier.

How these Issues would be Addressed through Theories and Principles:

After identifying and outlining the flaws found in the original Basic Bible Seminar 1 module, the next step was now to search for learning theories and principles that can be utilized to address these issues and gaps in the module. After an extensive search, a set of theories, principles, and models were found to align with the aspects

of the module to be redesigned which was subsequently applied in the development of the material.

To start, the first concern that needs to be addressed pertains to the modality of the materials to be created, which as identified to be in the form of digital and print materials consisting of both text and illustrations. After determining this, the **“Table of Affordances and Limitations of Modalities”** by Nunes and Gaible (2002) was employed first to evaluate the advantages and limitations of the modalities that were chosen, which is in the forms of text and images presented through digital infographics and booklets as aforementioned.

Regarding the affordances, it was found out that the combination of these modalities allows for the visual presentation of complex information, engages and motivates many learners, is cost-effective to develop, can be easily copied, shared, and used, and provides learners with specific and concrete information. These advantages align well with the chosen approaches of technology integration and open education, which I used to guide the design and development of all the materials.

With that said, in terms of limitations, one notable concern is that these materials require access to digital devices, electricity, and internet connectivity, which could be problematic especially considering how while all target audience members have digital devices, some may not consistently have a stable internet connection. Furthermore, another consideration was that extended reading sessions may lead to fatigue in the part of the learner. Identifying these limitations proved to be essential as it allowed the employment of methods aiming to address them through the integration of subsequent theories designed to overcome these challenges. After having a solid understanding of the affordances and limitations of the material, the

Visual Principles of Instructional Media and Technologies for Learning presented by Nash, L. (2015) were applied as a guiding framework in developing the materials.

From the list of principles outlined by **Nash, L. (2015)**, the first one utilized in designing the material is the **principle of alignment** which would be used to organize the space that should be utilized for the content. In this particular case, the proponent would incorporate a common edge axis and margin to help guide the user's eye to the space in which the content should appear while at the same time making a uniform look for the module.

Afterwards, **Nash, L. (2015)'s principle of balance** would be incorporated to ensure that the design feels stable and harmonious. This would be applied through the use of justified text alignment to provide a sense of uniformity within the body of text and pairing illustrations whenever possible to balance out the material in the number of visuals in text form and in image form which provides dynamicity for the material.

Accompanying the previous two principles would be the use of the **principle of arrangement with proximity** which refers to how objects or elements that are close to each other are perceived as related or grouped together. This principle would be incorporated in the creation of the material to induce perceived relationships and pairings between illustrations, thereby making it easier for the user to correlate which illustration refers to which text. Following this would be pairing the corresponding illustrations to the text that it relates to and keeping it close for easy recognition of patterns.

Afterwards, in designing the general theme of the materials, the principle of **figure-ground contrast** would be utilized to ensure harmonious relationship between elements in front and in the background of the material such that the elements in front are emphasized.

Last but not the least, the **principle of consistency** will be applied to glue all the previous principles together through ensuring uniformity and coherence of elements within a layout or across multiple designs, thereby ensuring that the overall design is visually harmonious and predictable, which helps in reinforcing the overall message and improving the user experience.

Another theory to be applied in the design and creation of the materials is **Mayer's Multimedia Learning Theory (1997)** which would be used to support the incorporation of the previous principles. In essence, this theory proposes that deeper learning is achieved when information is presented using both words and graphics rather than text alone, based on the assumption that there are two primary channels for learning: auditory and visual. These channels work together to process information into working memory. For the materials to be developed in this project, which would be designed to be compatible with both digital and printed formats for distribution to parish members after the project, direct integration of video elements would not be considered to prevent the need for extensive editing and restructuring for print. 4 principles from the theory will be applied in the designing of the material, the first one being the **Multimedia Principle** which in essence suggests that presenting relevant graphics with text rather than just text wherein Static or dynamic graphics combined with text can often communicate more effectively and efficiently than just text alone by presenting concepts and principles as a visual schema (Ramlatchan, M., 2019). This principle from the Multimedia Theory aligns with the

use of the previous principles in the sense that it similarly recommends the utilization of illustrations and static images that correspond to the written text to provide a better visual schema for a more efficient organization of information and content while at the same time making it more appealing for the target readers of the material.

Another Principle to be utilized in the material that was taken from **Mayer's Multimedia Learning Theory (1997)** will be the **Spatial contiguity Principle** which will be used in alignment with the **principle of arrangement with proximity** through placing text and graphics related to the aforementioned text near each other instead of placing it far from each other to avoid unnecessary confusion in the part of the readers of the material.

Aside from the previous two principles, the **Multimedia Learning Theory (1997)**'s **signalling principle** which in essence discusses the importance of highlighting content from the module will also be utilized in the designing of the material. In this particular case, signalling would be applied in the form of highlighting text, using bold font, italicizing, and underlining specific phrases and words within a body of text to emphasize it and signify its importance.

Last but not the least is the application of the theory's **Segmenting Principle** which states that a continuous complex presentation should instead be broken down into shorter more manageable chunks which will be applied through segmenting the topics of the material into various sections through the use of headers that group content in accordance with their type. This strategy of segmenting to be utilized would later be integrated along with the manual guides created by Proponent 2 of the joint-project into a complete Basic Bible 1 Module in the latter part of the development process.

Considering how the content of the original manual was very lengthy and not spaced appropriately, **Sweller's (1988) Cognitive Load Theory** is also planned to be integrated. To provide a brief background about the theory, Cognitive Load Theory (CLT), as outlined by Benjamin and Main (2022), serves as an instructional design framework centered on how the human brain processes and retains information. First introduced in the late 1980s, the theory primarily proposes that learning is most effective when the learning environment is aligned with the brain's cognitive capabilities. According to Benjamin and Main (2022), this theory builds upon well-established concepts related to information processing and storage. Key ideas include the separation of human memory into long-term and working memory, the concept that processing new information adds a "cognitive load" to working memory, which can influence learning outcomes, and the understanding that knowledge is stored in long-term memory as schemas. In the case of the materials to be developed, cognitive load theory will be utilized to improve the material using two concepts under the theory.

First is the **Intrinsic Load** which essentially explains how there is an inherent difficulty to every learning tasks, and that this said difficulty is primarily influenced by the learner's prior knowledge of the topic which according to Sweller can only be mitigated by modifying the nature of the learning material or by altering the cognitive tasks or processes involved in learning (Benjamin & Main, 2022). Following this principle, it can be deduced that the content of the original Basic bible Seminar 1 contains heavy intrinsic load due to the topics covered and a number of the terms used which can be challenging to read for the target audience of the project. Such a case would then lead to increased risk of the readers having cognitive overload

which results in the learner not being able to process the information properly. Moreover, the module being too complicated could lead to a loss of interest in the part of the target audience as they would be overwhelmed with the number of pages. In this regard, the strategy to be employed following this principle would first be to divide the content of the material into different sections which would then be divided again into various subsections while still maintaining it as one file. These sections will serve to provide “breathing space” to the target audience while they navigate each piece of content. Similarly, increasing the font size of the written content to make it easier to read and **decompress** the body of texts will be considered.

The second concept under **Sweller’s (1988) Cognitive Load Theory** that will be utilized in the project refers to the **Germane Load** which pertains to elements within the material that is used to facilitate information processing. This principle will be manifested in the material through the inclusion of infographics and charts to make understanding easier for certain parts of the content which in turn helps in the ease and efficiency of processing information and building up schemas.

Last but not the least is the application of the Theory of Behaviorism in the context of learning. In the case of the project, the utilization of this theory, particularly on the use of positive reinforcers to create habits via incentives under Operant Conditioning will be applied through the development of Digital Certificates which can be revised to fit multiple purposes for events within the parish.

Development Phase

In this development stage, the actual process of developing the material was classified into three main sections with each section pertaining to a particular stage in the development process.

A. Forming the “Skeleton” of the Material

The first stage of the development process is outlined as the Skeleton stage as this is the general outline of the material and the platform that would be utilized to create it was completed.

- **The Platform:** Starting with the Platform, Canva.com was chosen as the main platform to be used in developing the material as it offered various features and elements that enable multiple ways to customize the material.
- **The Canvas Resolution:** From the various Canvas sizes available in the platform, the Church Booklet size resolution was chosen which is **14.8 x 21 centimeter** to be exact considering the type of material to be developed which would be later consolidated into a module.
- **The Margin:** In accordance with the earlier design principles outlined, one of the first steps accomplished was to create a margin to guide the placement of the content of the material. In this regard, a **1 inch per side border margin** was followed to provide enough “white space and breathing room on each side.
- **The Color Scheme:** Following the visual design principles outlined, the color scheme chosen for the materials to be developed are **warm colors** for more appeal and vibrancy which in this case was the color **orange**. Another color scheme that was prominently used in the material is the use of

monochromatic colors to accentuate the color of the illustrations to be placed, thereby giving it more emphasis.

B. Shaping the “Flesh” of the Material

- **The Font Style and Size:** After completing the general outline of the material, the next stage of the development process was taken which pertains to the actual content to be included in the material. The first step that I took is choosing the font styles and sizes to be used. In the case of font styles, **CINZEL and Glacial Indifference** were chosen as the main font styles due to clarity and thickness of letters. As for the Font Sizes, they are **fs 20 (headers), fs 16 (subheaders), and fs 13 (body-text)**.
- **The Cover Pages:** Moving on, the next aspect of the materials developed were the cover pages which are created following the design principles outlined in the design stage of the project. Each cover created includes the **Title of the module, the conference day, the section of the module, and the particular topic** under that section which were all included to **provide clarity and avoid confusion** on the part of the viewers with regards to which part of the module they are actually reading.
- **The Main Text:** After accomplishing the previous parts of the design process, the main content of the material is now ready to be placed into the “skeleton” of the material that was created. In the placement of the text, the proponent followed the design principles that was earlier outlined pertaining to the **proper organization** of the content such that **enough allowance was provided to give breathing space**. Similarly, the content was placed while

taking into consideration the illustrations that would be added later to **ensure alignment** in the illustration to be placed in relation to the text that it is supporting.

Attaching the “Skin” of the material

- **The Illustrations:** Now that the main content of the material is placed accordingly in their appropriate spaces provided to them, it is now time to polish the material through including illustrations to accompany and complement the text, making it more **visually appealing** while also making the **processing of information a lot easier** as outlined in the design principles that was utilized. To avoid potential confusion on the part of the viewers, the **illustrations that correspond to a body of text are placed near to each other to establish a relationship.**
- **The Text Highlights:** Last but not the least, in accordance with the signalling principle, I highlighted key words and phrases from the bodies of text to make it easier for the users to read and view the most important parts of the material which also helps in the processing of information as the viewers can choose to focus on the main points of the content in their learning.

Cost of Development

Considering that the material developed was in a digital form, there are virtually no monetary costs in its development as I utilized free elements and features from the Canva platform which further exemplified and highlighted the main advantage of

technology integration in the creation and dissemination of instructional materials within the parish.

Creation of the full Basic Bible Seminar 1 Module

After compiling the developed materials, the next step was then to integrate said materials alongside the manual section of the module developed by Mark (proponent 2) to finally create the full Basic Bible Seminar 1 Module that was to be developed under the joint-project. In this part, we coordinated with each other and collaborated in placing our separate developed materials and creating the miscellaneous sections of the full module which include the table of contents, the numbering of the pages, the program flow, and the authors' final notes and acknowledgements.

Producing a sample Printed Booklet of the Module

After finalizing the module, we decided to produce one physical copy of the module which would be in the form of a booklet. With regards to the printing cost, we searched for printing shops that can print the booklet properly to which we unfortunately were not successful as most printing shops that we went to did not know how to print a material in a booklet form. Hence, we ultimately decided that I would be the one to print the booklet considering I have some background in the use of Adobe Acrobat for booklet printing. After the booklet had been successfully printed, we proceeded to book-bind it which cost us 200 pesos. Including the printing cost via estimation, we realized that a fully colored high quality copy of the Basic Bible Seminar 1 module that we developed would cost around 500-800 to create. This became quite the challenge since having it cost this much means that reproduction of the material would be limited. In this case, alternative means of

resolving this issue were sought to which the idea of photocopying came to my head. Photocopying, which can either be monochrome or colored, is much cheaper compared to full on printing and thus, could serve as an alternative means of producing a physical copy of the module for much cheaper in exchange for a drop in the quality.

Implementation Phase

Pilot Testing the Module

After successfully developing the newly redesigned module for the Basic Bible Seminar 1, testing the module with the aim being to gauge the reaction and experience of the target audience to the module as well as to see whether the project's goals and achievements were met had been conducted. The initial Pilot testing of the module was planned to be conducted through online means in accordance with the technology-integration approach taken for the project and the nature of the produced output which is in the form of a digital module that is compatible for printing. The main visual aid support material used for the pilot testing was a short powerpoint presentation outlining the key contents to be discussed in the seminar which was developed by the proponents.

Dissemination of the Module

The implementation phase officially started with the dissemination of the produced module digitally to the target audience on August 21, 2024 (the BA Core Group) via social media platforms alongside invitations to the upcoming pilot testing seminar which we set on August 23, 2024 due to it being a holiday. Similarly, the produced physical copy of the module in the form of a booklet was presented to Sister Rosa and Father Manuel before the implementation to view the physical copy of the module.

The Pilot Testing Seminar

At the day of the pilot testing seminar, a short dry run was conducted together with sister Reyn to orient her about the topics to be discussed through the seminar which primarily compose of 4 main parts as indicated in the powerpoint presentation which are as follows: (1) a short Introduction for this meeting followed by the Discussion of the purpose and features of the module, (2) followed by the main material of the module which had been in the form the 4 conference topics, (3) the main material serving as guide for the facilitators in the form of a guide manual, to then be followed by (4) a summary and discussion of all the topics discussed. To provide opportunities for the audience to provide feedback and evaluation, short question and answer sections were added in between the seminar topics to be followed by an open forum after the last part of the seminar. Aside from the goal of providing the audience with multiple opportunities to inquire or provide insights, this question and answer sections were also added to provide a breathing room for the audience to better digest the topics presented by Sister Reyn. Last but not the least, before ending the session, learners were oriented about their digital participation certificates, the feedback and evaluation survey to be sent via social media platforms and

accomplished by them digitally alongside a video and release form so we can disclose the data from the forms that they had accomplished.

This 1st seminar session was followed afterwards by a 2nd seminar session with the only difference being in the group of participants involved in that they were outsiders and had no connection whatsoever to Mary the Queen Parish contacted through convenience sampling. The second session was conducted in order to explore the future prospects of whether individuals who have no prior knowledge would still be able to understand the seminar and module which provides insights on its applicability and effectiveness outside of the target audience specifically composed of the BA core group. In this regard, the flow of the 2nd seminar session was made to be mostly similar to the first one except for the number of question and answer section portions which had been incorporated as one open forum at the end of the seminar to be followed by the awarding of participation certificates and the handing out of the feedback and evaluation forms.

Evaluation Phase

Feedback and Evaluation Forms

Three evaluation forms were developed following open-access general material and seminar feedback form samples which were then revised to include relevant questions specific to the BBS 1 module, the seminar conducted, and the context of the participants as part of Mary the Queen parish institution. Considering that the pilot-implementation was for the final output (module), the content of the evaluation survey includes content that is relevant to both the materials and the manual integrated in the module.

Types of Questions included:

- **Background Inquiry:** They are basic questions that inquire about the background of the respondent. In the case of this questionnaire, this included questions such as their name and their connection to the parish.
- **Likert Scale:** A significant portion of the questions included in the feedback and evaluation questionnaire were in Likert-scale form to gauge the feedback of the target audience in terms of intensity through 1-5.
- **Either-Or Preference:** An either-or question was included in the questionnaire tackling their preference between digital and printed to have an idea which form the module should be tailored more towards in the future.
- **Open Suggestion:** A section of the questionnaire was dedicated towards an open-ended question asking for specific insights of the respondent to give them an opportunity to provide in-depth feedback.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Starting first with the data gathered from the feedback form disseminated to the BA Core Group, it was notable that 7 out of 8 respondents expressed positive feedback and evaluation on the materials developed and included in the module as well as the seminar conducted which was the powerpoint presentation and the accompanying script utilized for the seminar and the developed digital certificate. In particular, the design principles that were utilized and the use of illustrations received a score consisting mostly 4 out 5 and 5 out 5 ratings.

A similar case could be observed with regards to the ratings of how the content had been organized if it was easy to read and navigate through for the audience. As for whether the participants preferred the printed version of the module or the digital one, the results had been a straight half with 50% preferring a digital one and the other 50% preferring a printed one in the form of a booklet. It is worth noting that there was one respondent who expressed dissatisfaction with the module as a whole as reflected by the survey answers of mostly 1 out of 5 and 2 out of 5 ratings which can be considered an outlier or a special case. Moving on with the data gathered from the second round of online pilot testing seminar in which the participants were not part of the Parish, majority of the audience similarly expressed positive feedback with regards to the organization and design principles utilized in the materials developed despite having no connection whatsoever and not being a member of the Parish and Basic Bible Study 1 Seminar which the material is intended for.

This points toward a positive outlook for the materials made in general as it received mostly positive feedback from both groups of individuals as it means that it could prove to be useful as even individuals who are not necessarily members of the parish or who have prior knowledge on the topic are able to understand and learn from it. Relating this to the overarching goals and objectives of the joint-project, it could be said that the material created had been able to help in addressing the issues within the parish that pertain to the lack of appropriate instructional materials being utilized for learning sessions such as seminars as is the case with the BBS 1 seminar wherein the module being used were pure text and was also a scanned copy which made certain portions and words hard to distinguish or understand.

Similarly, one of the main objectives of the project is the introduction and use of technology-integrated instructional materials that allow for easier dissemination and

access in the part of the learners while also cutting the need to procure and produce physical materials which cost money. In a similar fashion, the goal of improving the appeal of the material to the learners to encourage engagement in their part had been achieved as per the results of the feedback evaluation survey wherein majority expressed positive feedback in the module developed.

As for their recommendations, there were two which were for the material to be divided into sections and that the number of songs to be decreased in order to give way for more time to discuss the conference topics. With regards to the suggestion of decreasing the number of songs as part of their recommendations, discussions are currently being held together with father Manuel since the matter would similarly be up for decision first by father Manuel as the parish priest and next, the Diocese of Antipolo which is planned to be included in the future continuation of the project.

Direct Feedback from the Parish Priest:

After collecting and analyzing the feedback of the participants during the 2 pilot-testing seminars, the data generated through google forms was digitally forwarded to father Manuel for viewing. Afterwards, an in-person discussion was scheduled wherein father Manuel provided direct feedback with regards to the project which contained the following main topics:

- **Feedback of the Module created:** According to father Manuel, the module created served the initial purpose and objectives that it was intended to serve and that being able to develop a sample booklet had been a big deal since there are individuals who appreciate a physical copy more than a digital one so it was good that we had the idea to create one for him to evaluate. The color scheme, arrangement of content, and the inclusion of other materials

according to Fathe Manuel had also been handled correctly and is indeed helpful for facilitators and trainee facilitators of Basic Bible Seminar 1.

- **The Project's Impact to the Institution:** Furthermore, it was very helpful for the parish especially the youth ministry considering that it resulted in a major project credited to the youth ministry which had little to none major projects accomplished during the time that he served as the parish priest in the institution which spanned for a total of 4 years. According to father Manny, although there have been plans for conducting projects before by youth ministry members, none had been fully accomplished as the members had been moving away from the parish the moment they got to step into the Diocese.
- **Future Plans for the Module:** Last but not the least, father Manuel discussed his future plans for the module that we created wherein he discussed that after fully reviewing the module, he plans to forward it to the Diocese of Antipolo for further screening and checking with overall goal being to make it the official Basic Bible 1 Module for the Parish. According to the Parish Priest, the challenge in this part would be that it was designed to be conducted for 2 days instead of the original 5 nights in the module which would be the major part that would be reviewed.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary and Conclusion

This project explored the application of instructional design principles and theories in a non-formal educational setting through the chosen locale of Mary the Queen parish which is a religious institution that also serves as an educational institution through providing its ministry members with seminars. One particular seminar was focused upon in this project which had been the Basic Bible Seminar 1 conducted by the church for a subgroup of the parish's Youth ministry which are the BA core Youth group. Digital print-compatible instructional materials were developed and evaluated through controlled distribution of the material followed by a Pilot Testing Seminar for the gathering of feedback and recommendations through survey questionnaires.

The project was able to uncover an institution-specific challenge pertaining to the use of instructional design principles, particularly on the use of gamification in the material which contradicted with the nature and beliefs of a number of the members of the parish. Similarly, the project was able to explore digital integration within the parish through garnering feedback on the use of digital materials and online seminars as another medium to provide learning to the members aside from face to face sessions. The results of the evaluation showed 50% of the participants preferring digital materials while the other half preferred the printed version of the module with major considerations being the cost of production, convenience in accessing, portability, and adaptability.

Key Challenges Encountered

Availability of the Parish Priest

Throughout the project, one key challenge that shaped the direction of the project had been the availability of Father Manuel Cuevas as the project gatekeeper and adviser. The main idea for choosing Father Manuel Cuevas to be the project gatekeeper was due to his position as the top decision-maker in the institution which should make the project easier to accomplish. Although it indeed made the project smooth sailing in terms of getting approval for the various actions and steps that was planned, various aspects of the project took a hit through not being able to properly set a schedule with Father Manuel due to his busy schedule as a parish priest coupled with the events that had transpired in the institution that he was required to personally attend to. Thus, in order to circumvent this, online contact with Father Manuel was established to be able to converse with him outside of the parish which indeed lessened the difficulty of coordinating with him although the issue of his availability still reflected in his short replies. Another step that was taken in order to help address this was scheduling an appointment directly in the parish's office to provide updates about the availability of Father Manuel which was used in retrieving the signed gatekeeper consent form.

Finding Resource Materials within the Parish

Another key challenge that was encountered that arguably shaped the direction of the project was finding resource materials within the parish that are contextualized for the youth ministry which was due to the youth ministry not being active in terms of activities that they themselves organized. Not finding a resource material in the initial stages of the project led me to take a general approach with regards to the contents

that would be included in the materials that would be developed. The significance of having a resource material was further exemplified after being able to acquire one through Sister Rosa which had been the Original Basic Bible Seminar 1 Module wherein the direction of the project took a more streamlined and narrow approach targeting a specific seminar that was in actual need of an appropriate material/module. Looking back, this challenge would not have been resolved if not for attending the Basic Bible Seminar 1.

Personally Getting to know the Target Audience

A similar issue that snowballed into a significant concern was the need to know the target audience which was the BA Core group at a more personal level and maintain the connection that was initially established during the Basic Bible Seminar 1. Aside from being able to get more honest answers and suggestions from them through building rapport, this was needed in preparation for the pilot testing of the project to ensure an easier acceptance rate of invitations. The steps taken to resolve this is through attending post-BBS 1 youth ministry assemblies conducted every Saturday which include the youth core-group in the list of participants and attendees. In this regard, extra time had been allotted to attend these assemblies just to get to know the target audience. Looking back, considering the amount of time that had been spent in attending these assemblies, a better utilization of opportunities and time-management could have been made in my part to make the most of the time spent which I was not able to do due to being caught up with learning the topics being discussed during said assemblies led by Sister Rosa.

Planning and Scheduling of Implementation

Another issue that was encountered throughout the project pertains to the planning and the scheduling of implementation which we changed a lot of times due to issues of availability in the part of the target audience and facilitators and the costs of conducting an in-person implementation. In the case of an in-person implementation, it was intended that physical copies of the module in the form of booklets are to be utilized but then after seeing the costs of producing a single copy, another issue emerged which is that where would we get the funds to produce multiple high quality copies of the module. One approach that was initially thought was to produce only one module to be shared by the participants. However, this was found to be lacking and would skew the opinion of the participants due to having a negative experience. As for the online pilot testing, one of the major issues that was experienced was the lack of participation in the part of the target audience as only a select few participants joined in the conversation and provided their insights. In order to maintain participation, the approach taken was to ask the participants to react with likes and hearts whenever they agree with what was being said. Although this form of participation is lacking in depth, it was able to serve the purpose of encouraging participation in the part of the audience.

Aligning the Strategies and Theories with the Context of the Institution

One of the biggest challenges that was encountered in the project was tailoring the approaches, strategies, and theories that had been planned to be included in the specific context of the Institution since in a real-life setting there exists certain factors and variables that may influence and affect the applicability and effectiveness of the approaches that was planned to be utilized. This conflict had been apparently observed in the design stage of the project wherein upon expanding the network of

church individuals involved in the project, difference in opinions occurred between said individuals had occurred pertaining to the use of gamification which is an institution-specific restriction considering that it was not anticipated how it might have traditions that could conflict with the strategies that are to be employed. In fear of further delays and issues in the next set of processes to be accomplished, it was ultimately decided to put this aspect of the project on hold to be explored again in the future. Looking back, such an issue could have been tackled in a different approach which could have yielded a different result wherein gamification would be applied which would be included as part of the paper's recommendations.

Limitations of Free Accounts in Meeting Platforms and Sites

One of the limitations that was discovered in the use of online meeting platforms and sites for conducting online seminars was that not having a premium or paid account drastically limits and restricts the options and opportunities to utilize it. Such had been the case for Zoom and Googlemeet platforms wherein group meetings hosted by an individual with a free account only lasted for 40-60 minutes before the call automatically drops. This time limit restrains the meeting's length which in turn would lead to two options, (1) the host needs to adjust the meeting's contents to fit 1 hour or (2) the host would divide the content of the meeting into separate parts if it would last above an hour which is very inconvenient and defeats the purpose of doing an online seminar in the first place. In this regard, it could be said that even if an online approach was taken, there would still be costs.

Recommendations

Looking back at the full run of the capsule project from start to finish in reference to the aforementioned key challenges experienced, it is evident that several aspects and processes followed particularly in the documentation aspects of the capsule project were not done excellently and completely as there had been instances wherein the conversations and discussion that should serve as primary evidence were not fully documented as the evidence that the meetings occurred had only been through images and notes taken of the venue or institution during the visit. During one of the initial visits on the Parish wherein the proponent discussed the project with Father Manuel, the Parish Priest asked to focus on the discussion and take notes afterwards as form of documentation which could be due to Father Manuel's personal preferences when discussing something or due to the place the discussion is happening which is at the parish wherein such actions could be discouraged. In this regard, it is recommended that if possible, a change of venue could be proposed or permissions for recording while the conversation happens be asked.

Similarly, it is seen that there had been issues with regards to communicating with relevant personnel, particularly father Manuel due to his busy schedule following the back to back events that had transpired within the parish especially during the second half of the project's timeline.

Another observable critical event during the whole timeline of the capsule had been the pivot from designing a material that is generally useful for the parish into redesigning a module that is already part of the parish and is to be used for the upcoming training of the Core BA youth members as the next youth facilitator for BBS 1. Opting for this route also ensures that there would be a real need and use for

the material already. There has also been a noticeable increase in enthusiasm on the part of the institution members when the material to be developed is one that they are already planning to utilize in the current program.

Last but not the least, the project experienced issues with regards to the application of gamification principles and elements in the material as a method of increasing appeal and engagement of the users which came about during the second half of the project's timeline after getting acquainted with more elderly members of the parish as opinions were divided in the idea of gamification as there had been opinions that gamifying the materials/module could lead to learners equating going to these seminars and engaging with the material do to it being entertaining when it should be taken seriously and as such they should instead be engaging and going to these seminars because they are interested in the content itself of the material and seminar. This led to the gamification aspect of the project to be put on hold with gamification elements such as the use of Frame.vr as initially proposed where heavy gamification of sessions are applied. With that said, gamification was still able to be applied through incorporating short game activities developed earlier in the initial material created. In this regard, it is recommended to look more into the opinions of higher-ups when proposing a project as there might be differences in opinions that would lead to the approval process of certain aspects of the project to be a lot harder.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A: Instructional Design Plan

Needs Analysis:

Figure 1a. Printed Summary of the Interviews and discussions conducted with the Parish Priest as part of the Needs Analysis of the Locale and the Target Learners.

Figure 1b. Basic Bible Seminar 1 Certificate awarded for participating in the Basic Bible Seminar 1 for the purpose of data gathering of Learner Demographic

Figure 1c. Basic Bible Seminar 1 head facilitators along with the youth Ministry members from which the target audience and participants for the project were selected from.

<https://test49020.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/bbs-1-manual-1-1.pdf>

Link 1a. Hyperlink to the Basic Bible Seminar 1 Module from which the content of the updated instructional materials were pulled from.

Instructional Design

MODE	INSTRUMENT	AFFORDANCES	LIMITATIONS
Text	Books/ magazines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Portable > Durable > Can present complex information > Sequential structure guides learner > Little eyestrain > Moderate cost of development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Difficult to modify (as in localization, updating, etc.) > Requires literacy plus higher-order thinking skills > Content is difficult to extract for use in other resources > High per-unit cost of publication
	Web page	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Dynamic and easily modified > Hyperlinks enable nonsequential navigation > Low cost of development and very low publishing costs > Supports interactivity (e.g., navigation, user-entered information, etc.) > Can support assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Nonsequential structure may obscure critical information or cause confusion > Reading may cause fatigue > Requires PC, electricity, connection > Potential additional system requirements (e.g., Java, plug-ins)
Images	Printed photos, maps, and schematic drawing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Concrete, specific, detailed information > Appropriate for learners with "visual intelligence" > Engaging and motivating for many learners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Low information value relative to text > Resistant to reuse by learners > "Visual literacy" skills required for best use > High cost of reproduction
	Digital photos, maps, and schematic drawings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Affordances similar to printed photos > Easily copied, shared, and used > Low costs for reproduction and publishing > Can be data-based or Web-served for delivery to handheld computers and other "anytime, anywhere" devices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Limitations similar to printed photos > Require PC and electricity, possibly an Internet connection

Figure 1d. An excerpt from Nunes and Gaible (2002)'s Table of Affordances and Limitations of Modalities which was utilized in assessing the applicability and validity of the chosen modalities in designing the instructional materials.

cognitive load

mcdreeamieusings.com @mcdreeamie

Figure 1e. an Illustration of the 3 categories of cognitive load as discussed in the Cognitive Load Theory which was utilized in designing the material.

Instructional Development

Implementation

Material/Resource	Utilization	Procurement
Printer	A Printer had been utilized for the procurement of the hard copy of the constructed materials inside the module	The printer needed for the project had been provided by the proponent with the institution volunteering to cover costs of printing.

Ink	Ink was needed in printing the hard a copy of the instructional materials inside the module	Along with the aforementioned printer, the corresponding ink cartridges needed for the project was similarly provided by the proponent.
Paper	The hard copy of the instructional material and the instructor's manual would be printed in paper.	The papers in which the hard copy of the material would be printed in would also be provided by the proponents.
Laptops/Computer	To be utilized by the proponents in the designing and procurement of the instructional design outputs for the proposed project. Also used for the pilot testing of the material	The laptops to be used by the proponents would be provided by themselves, same for the instructors and learners if they want to use one.
Mobile Phones	Utilized by the instructors and the learners in accessing the instructional materials developed. Also used for the pilot testing of the material.	The mobile phones to be used by the learners would be provided by themselves,

Internet Connection	Although utilizing the learning materials would not require a fast internet connection, it is needed to access it. Similarly, it is needed by the proponent in designing and creating the aforementioned outputs for the proposed project.	The internet connection needed by the learners to access the materials would be produced by themselves when accessing them asynchronously.
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Figure 1f. A breakdown of the materials and tools utilized for the pilot testing seminar implementation to be conducted digitally through online meeting platforms.

APPENDIX B: Instructional Materials Produced

Figure 2a. A digital transcript of one of the prayers included in the set of prayer materials produced as part of the Basic Bible 1 Module.

Figure 2b. A digital lyrics of one of the worship songs included in the set of instructional materials produced as part of the Basic Bible 1 Module.

<https://test49020.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/copy-of-mqp-bbs1-module-1.pdf>

Link 2a. A hyperlink to a Digital Copy of the developed Basic Bible Seminar 1 module

<https://test49020.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/bbs-1-module-pilot-testing-ppt.pdf>

Link 2b. A hyperlink to a Digital copy of the Powerpoint presentation utilized for the Pilot Testing Seminar 1 and 2 of the developed Basic Bible Seminar 1 Module

Figure 2c. An Image of a Blank Certificate of Participation awarded to the individuals who participated in the Basic Bible 1 Seminar Pilot Testing Seminar.

APPENDIX C: Documentation Logs

[EDS 143: Program plan Implementation Recordings](#)

Link 3a. Link to the google drive folder containing the recorded evaluation seminar 1 for the created module

[EDS 143: Program plan Implementation Recordings](#)

Link 3b. Link to the google drive folder containing the recorded evaluation seminar 2 for the created module

APPENDIX D: Project Logs

This log is for the students in the Bachelor of Education Studies (BES) program at the University of the Philippines Open University. The student should complete the log after each session, to be validated by the project gatekeeper/ external adviser, depending on the chosen project. The last column is for the project's gatekeeper on the student's work. When the project is finished, a scanned copy of this log sheet shall be submitted as part of the special project portfolio.

Student's name: <u>Anthony Jonathan T. Rosantina</u>	Batch of entry in UPOU: <u>1st 2020-2021</u>
Student number: <u>2020-03386</u>	Contact number: <u>0956-021-2107</u>
Email address: <u>anthonyrosantina75@gmail.com</u>	
Academic Term: <input type="checkbox"/> 1st term <input type="checkbox"/> 2nd term <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 3rd term	AY: <u>2023-2024</u>
Project Locale: <u>Mary the Queen Parish, Taytay Rizal</u>	
Student's Project Main Task: <u>Development of Materials</u>	

Project Week	Specific Date	Specific Time	Duration	Validated by	Highlights	Insights	Gatekeeper's Feedback
Week 1-2					Search for Institutions Coordinate with EDS 199 FIC for the joint-project	Searching for an institution is actually very tedious and time consuming as per my experience as I needed to coordinate and establish initial communications which took up a lot of my time.	

Week 7-8					Meeting with Parish Priest Coordination with the Institution's youth ministry	When I got to have a lengthy talk with the Parish Priest is when I realized the importance of having in-depth information of what the Institution needs and wants to be changed through the project.	✓ Manuel S. Cuna 8/29/24
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Week 13-14	June 4-6, 2024				Retrieved Fully Signed Consent Form Looking for Reference Materials	Seeking and looking for reference materials within Institutions, especially documents require continuous effort. Moreover, even with effort, it may still take time so it is important to plan ahead of time with regards to this.	✓ Manuel S. Cuna 8/29/24
Week 15-16					Continuation of search for a Previous Youth Ministry Reference Material that could be of use. Material Development	During this part, development of the materials are still ongoing, but more effort is now being diverted towards accomplishing what I believe is a much more important aspect of the project.	
Week 17-18	July 6-7, 2024				Received Invitation to attend BBS 1 Seminar Attended BBS 1 Seminar Obtained BBS 1 Certificates Met and Coordinated with Sister Rosa	This time period became the most significant pivotal event in the project as we got to attend BBS 1 Seminar and obtain more knowledge and expertise with regards to the Bible which would translate towards the final material to be created. We also got acquainted with Sister Rosa whom provided us with guidance moving forward.	✓ Manuel S. Cuna 8/29/24

Week 19-20	July 20, 2024				<p>Requested for a copy of the BBS 1 module</p> <p>Decision to make the BBS 1 module the main Material for the project.</p> <p>Creation of the Materials</p> <p>Development of redesigned BBS 1 module together with Mark</p>	<p>After lengthy talks and discussions with Sister Rosa, we were able to secure an official youth ministry document in the form of the BBS 1 Module which became the main material to be developed while incorporating content from previous one.</p>	
Week 21-22				<p>Finalizing of the BBS 1 module material</p> <p>Planning for Pilot Testing</p>	<p>To ensure that the pilot testing of the material would be completed without issues, this time period was utilized to prepare for the upcoming Pilot implementation. This is one of the most challenging weeks for me as I had been nervous about the success of the implementation.</p>		
Week 23-24	August 23, 2024			<p>Pilot Testing Week</p> <p>Printing of the developed module</p> <p>Accomplishing of Remaining requirements</p>	<p>Thankfully, the pilot implementation was a success as we were able to find a speaker/facilitator that would handle the short online seminar conducted.</p>	<p>✓ Manuel S. Cueto 8/29/2024</p>	

APPENDIX E: Consent Forms

Special Project in Bachelor of Education Studies

The first page of the consent form is to be accomplished by the students in the Bachelor of Education Studies (BES) program at the University of the Philippines Open University.

For our students: Kindly complete this form in consultation with the head of the institution and/or the person-in-charge, department head or supervisor, the special project gatekeeper, depending on where you will conduct the project.

Student's name: Anthony Jonathan Tabilisma Rosanting

Student number: 2020-03385 Batch of entry in UPOU: 1st Trimester 2020

Email address: anthonyrosanting75@gmail.com Contact number: 0956-021-8107

Academic Term: 1st term 2nd term 3rd term AY: 2023-2024

Special Project Outcomes

After completing the course, the student should be able to:

1. Apply knowledge of educational research analyzing and evaluating an educational issue or problem; OR apply knowledge of instructional design in developing and testing an instructional program, resource, or technology;
2. Critically reflect on their experiences as they complete their special project; and
3. Demonstrate ethical practice and desirable professional work attitudes and skills

Special Project Requirements

Project Preliminary Report the implementation sessions of the practicum plan with at least one:

- Instructional Design Project: implementation or testing of instructional materials/resources, technology-supported education/training programs/curriculum/ modules/courses, or learning systems that the student developed which will be evaluated by the gatekeeper/ external adviser from the project locale and the faculty-in-charge (FIC) in EDS 199
- Research Project: implementation of research project in an educational setting which will be evaluated by the gatekeeper/ external adviser from the project locale and the faculty-in-charge (FIC) in EDS 199

Class/Learner/
Program/ Needs Analysis an analysis/ report based on observation of actual practice, interview of teacher/ department head/ program head, and or other pre-assessment or evaluation tools

Project Plan a plan highlighting the specific activities and strategies that the student will implement to accomplish the assigned project task or work based on educational theories, concepts, and principles

Project Work the implementation sessions of the project plan with at least one:

- Instructional Design Project implementation or testing of instructional materials/resources, technology-supported education/training programs/curriculum/ modules/courses, or learning systems that the student developed which will be evaluated by the gatekeeper/ external adviser from the project locale and the faculty-in-charge (FIC) in EDS 199
- Research Project: implementation of research project in an educational setting which will be evaluated by the gatekeeper/

- external adviser from the project locale and the faculty-in-charge (FIC) in EDS 199
- Project ePortfolio the collection of documents, reports, and relevant attachments showcasing learning from and analysis of the whole practicum experience, and providing evidence of achievement and accomplishments
- Project eJournal a brief reflective journal on the insights gained, problems experienced and solutions made, and areas for improvement
- Project presentation the presentation of the highlights of the special project which will be assessed by the FIC and monitored by the BES Program Chair

Student's signature: [Signature] Date: June 01, 2020
 To the Head of Institution/ Practicum Supervisor,

I would like to express my deepest gratitude for extending your expertise and guidance to our student. With your help, our student will be able to achieve the objectives of the special project, gain invaluable knowledge and understanding of the work involved and required in the profession, as well as develops the skills needed in the field. Again, thank you very much.

Sincerely,
[Signature]

Asst. Prof. Leynard Gripal
 Faculty-In-Charge, 2T 23-24 EDS 199 – Special Project

Gatekeeper/ External Adviser's Approval

Duties of the Gatekeeper:

- assigns tasks
- guides student in his/her accomplishment of tasks
- encourages creativity and innovation
- monitors progress
- provides regular feedback and comments
- signs practicum logs
- evaluates teaching demonstration/implementation or testing of output

This signifies my consent for the BES student to conduct special project in our institution/ organization/community class provided that s/he will abide by our policies and regulations. I understand that the student is expected to showcase creative and innovative application of theories and principles that s/he has learned from your undergraduate program in an actual professional work; thus, we shall provide the student with opportunities for such endeavor.

Name and Signature above Printed Name: Rev. Fr. Manuel S. Cuevas
 Designation: Panish Priest
 Name of institution/ organization: Mary the Queen Panish
 Office number: (8) 653-7370 Email address: mcp.byty@gmail.com
 Date: 06.04.2024

APPENDIX F: Evaluation Tools

Module Evaluation Questionnaire:

Pilot testing Seminar Session 1 results

How well did the content of the module hold up to your expectation?

8 responses

Was the information and content presented in the module clear and easy to understand?

8 responses

How relevant do you think the content included in the module would be for you as a BBS 1 facilitator/trainee-facilitator?

8 responses

Were the interactive elements (if any) engaging and useful in enhancing your learning experience?

8 responses

How effective was the Seminar in fostering a closer relationship between you, your peers, and other youth leaders?

8 responses

How helpful were the activities listed in the module helpful in delivering instruction?

8 responses

Do you feel confident that you would be able to apply what you learned from the module in future BBS 1 seminars?

8 responses

Do you feel more prepared in conducting BBS 1 compared to before?

8 responses

Do you feel more prepared in conducting BBS 1 compared to before?

8 responses

How helpful was the instructional module in creating your presentation?

8 responses

Which do you prefer more for your learning preference, a digital or printed version of the module?

8 responses

How logically and coherently was the module content organized?

8 responses

How would you rate the visual appeal of the module (layout, design, images)

8 responses

How likely are you to recommend this module to others?

8 responses

How would you rate the overall clarity and organization of the seminar

8 responses

How relevant and applicable to your context as a BBS 1 facilitator/trainee-facilitator was the seminar content?

8 responses

How effectively did the facilitator communicate the key points of the module?

8 responses

Did the seminar provide sufficient opportunities for participation and interaction (e.g., Q&A, discussions, learning activities)?

8 responses

How engaging were the activities or interactive elements during the seminar?

8 responses

How would you rate the overall technical quality (e.g., audio, video, presentation slides) during the seminar?

8 responses

How satisfied were you with the seminar overall?

8 responses

Pilot testing Seminar Session 2 results

How well did the content of the module hold up to your expectation?

4 responses

Was the information and content presented in the module clear and easy to understand?

4 responses

Were the interactive elements (if any) engaging and useful in enhancing your learning experience?

4 responses

How effective was the Seminar in fostering a closer relationship between you, your peers, and other youth leaders?

4 responses

How helpful were the activities listed in the module helpful in delivering instruction?

4 responses

Which do you prefer more for your learning preference, a digital or printed version of the module?

4 responses

How logically and coherently was the module content organized?

4 responses

How would you rate the visual appeal of the module (layout, design, images)

4 responses

How likely are you to recommend this module to others?

4 responses

How would you rate the overall clarity and organization of the seminar

4 responses

How effectively did the facilitator communicate the key points of the module?

4 responses

Did the seminar provide sufficient opportunities for participation and interaction (e.g., Q&A, discussions, learning activities)?

4 responses

How engaging were the activities or interactive elements during the seminar?

4 responses

How would you rate the overall technical quality (e.g., audio, video, presentation slides) during the seminar?

4 responses

How satisfied were you with the seminar overall?

4 responses

